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HOW DO WE BUILD EFFECTIVE ONLINE STUDENT COMMUNITIES?

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ABSTRACT

Delivering engineering programmes online presents several challenges, including issues around effective technologies, digital access, and delivery of traditional hands-on project and laboratory activities. Reflection on these issues after a full year of online teaching suggests that despite initial difficulties, both educators and students have adapted well to online delivery of content, and indeed certain aspects such as video content and online quizzes have been very well received by students. However, significant challenges remain in creating effective social structures and peer groups which are vital for student learning, mental health and wellbeing.

This workshop explored how can we encourage students to build online communities. In particular, what structures and opportunities should be in place? What activities can we build into our programmes that embed social interaction? How can technology be used to facilitate this?

The workshop started with a short poll to gather information on participant experiences of teaching in an online environment verse face-to-face. It was facilitated using virtual breakout rooms with participants split into two groups. Group one focused on how we create an appropriate online environment while the second discussed what methods and technologies could be utilised to achieve this. Responses and contributions from each breakout session were gathered using the electronic collaboration platform Padlet. A summary of each area was created and disseminated.

This workshop was an excellent starting point in discussing the complexities of building and maintaining online student communities. The majority of participants felt they gained new ideas on how to encourage students to interact and moving forward are keen to try something new in their teaching. Participants found sharing their experiences with colleagues useful.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid switch to online modes of delivery in many institutions has brought with it a myriad of challenges for engineering programme delivery, including issues around effective technologies, digital access, and delivery of hands-on project and laboratory activities.

Reflection on these issues after an academic year of online teaching suggests that despite initial difficulties, both educators and students have adapted well to online delivery of content, and indeed certain aspects such as video content and online quizzes have been very well received by students. However, significant challenges remain in creating effective social structures and peer groups which are vital for student learning, mental health and wellbeing. Online delivery remains 'distant' (Ní She, *et al* 2019), not only is there a degree of separation between the educator and student but the student is also separated from their peers. Lui *et al* (2007) highlighted how online modes of delivery can lead to a sense of student isolation. To overcome this, it is important to embed opportunities and activities for engagement. Some activities within our school such as an ongoing reflective journal activity for Mathematics, involving online peer group feedback sessions, have been generally well received: *"I have thoroughly enjoyed being part of my group...it's been refreshing to be able to talk to people on my course and not just be watching lectures all day. They've been super helpful with any problems I've had."* However, managing these has been technically challenging and time intensive, and issues with engagement remain.

Drawing on the experiences from our own School, it is intended that this workshop is a starting point for collating best practices in building engaging online communities, with potential opportunity for further collaboration between workshop participants across various institutions. The workshop aimed to provide opportunities for participants to share experiences and both motivate and give confidence to those who want to try new forms of online engagement with their students. The intended learning outcomes were:

- Benefit from shared discussion of prior experiences both positive and negative.
- Gain ideas and methodologies for building online learning communities.
- Acquire understanding of how methods could be applied within own teaching context.
- Develop motivation and confidence to try new approaches.
- Gain access to a support network of peers building online communities within engineering education.

2 METHODOLOGY

This workshop targeted those who wished to share their experience of trying to develop an online student community. It was also an opportunity for those who are new to online delivery and looking for ideas to engage with more experienced colleagues. Online polls and breakout rooms were used to facilitate the workshop and gather information.

2.1 Workshop structure

A short introduction was given outlining the structure and to provide context to the activities used. The first activity involved asking participants to complete a short poll, using MS Forms. This was to determine the experiences within the group of online teaching and learning and to establish how participants felt about the delivery of content and engagement with students using online environments compared to face to face. Once the experiences poll was completed participants were asked to join one of two breakout rooms. Participants were

allowed to select which topic they would like to focus on. The theme of each breakout room was,

1. **Creating:** How do we put structures in place that will encourage students to engage. How does it become a natural part of the learning environment? How can we encourage students to build online communities?
2. **Methods:** How can technology be used to facilitate this? What activities can we build into our programmes that embed social interaction? How does the group size, dynamic and environment affect the approaches taken - Blended vs Online vs In-person? What pedagogical methods are key? How do we switch traditional group project and hands-on activities to an online format?

Responses and contributions from each session was gathered using electronic collaboration platform Padlet. This enabled participants to easily engage not only with the workshop facilitator but with each other. Using the platform gave the participants a choice of several of methods of interaction; oral, post comments or attachment of documents they would like to share. A discussion was held to allow participants to explain and elaborate upon the points they contributed to the Padlet. A summary from each breakout room was collated and disseminated back to the wider group at the end of the session.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Online vs Face-to-Face Experiences Poll

Figure 1 outlines the results from the initial poll which asked participants how challenging different issues were in an online environment compared to face-to-face teaching. Responses were provided by 12 participants.

Figure 1. Results from teaching experience poll looking at online vs face-to-face. Question posed: "In your experience, how challenging have the following issues been in an online environment compared to face-to-face teaching?"

As expected, experiences for the participants varied. 91% of participants found accessibility and flexibility of learning materials for students to either be the same or improved. In terms of inclusivity of learning opportunities for all, 58% of participants found this to be improved while 25% felt it was somewhat worse. Communication between participants and individual students

was varied and communication between students tended to be worse (66%). The majority felt that student engagement was either the same (42%) or worse (33%). Interestingly, 33% indicated that students' academic outcomes were worse compared to 25% who stated they had improved, whereas 42% confirmed student academic outcomes remained the same. Overall, the majority felt that student social outcomes, student wellbeing and staff wellbeing were worse using an online environment.

3.2 Breakout Rooms – Padlet Discussion Board

Table 1 and Table 2 provides a summary of the Padlet discussion boards that were used in the breakout rooms. Each breakout room focused on one area, with a series of questions within the topic posed and discussed. The link to the Padlet discussion boards is provided in row one of each table.

Table 1 Summary points from Padlet Board discussion 'Creating structures and opportunities for student community building online'.

<p>Link to Padlet Board: "Creating structures and opportunities for student community building online"</p> <p>https://qubeps.padlet.org/louisepick/mix0r1xjvglzxs3</p>
<p>Give a good example of a strategy you have used (or seen used) to encourage student community building online</p> <p>Setting up groups and maintaining them throughout the year. Designing group activities to encourage students to get to know one another, including collating the experiences of a group through a group CV, getting groups to share work with the class, present to class, and to provide peer feedback on other groups.</p> <p>Using appropriate techniques in tutorial sessions to encourage group interaction.</p> <p>Encouraging individual engagement, for example using of peer instruction questions, informal drop-in sessions, letting students set the agenda, encouraging use of cameras. Explaining the importance of engagement to students.</p>
<p>Have you experience of a strategy that did not work well?</p> <p>Making the assumption that students will know how to use the technologies. Not making questions challenging enough- the threshold for answering seems to be higher in virtual environments than physical. Difficulties in successful groupwork online in large classes. Not using the chat functions appropriately. Online "dating" to find a collaborator, video pitches to find appropriate group members, and online course cafes did not prove successful.</p>
<p>How do we make student community building a natural part of the online learning environment?</p> <p>Letting students create their own social spaces, many students did not "sign up" for online learning, so they might only want to communicate with their learning group via chats. Try to introduce students virtually in a social context before the course start. Dedicate time to social interaction in class, small talk, checking in.</p>
<p>What are the barriers to students to effective community building?</p> <p>Lack of motivation, lack of time, lack of self-confidence. Digital poverty - poor accessibility to internet/ computers e.g. Lack of social skills.</p>
<p>How do we as educators encourage students to interact online?</p> <p>Give them tasks they can only complete if they cooperate and interact.</p>
<p>How do we assess the effectiveness of our structures?</p> <p>Student feedback, grading.</p>

Any other points you wish to add?

One suggestion was to develop a digital communication/participation crash course.

Table 2. Summary points from Padlet Board discussion on “Methods to facilitate student community building online”

Link to Padlet Board: “Methods to facilitate student community building online”
<https://qubeys.padlet.org/louisepick/tu81n6slmzzgv45d>

What is the most useful technology that you have used (or seen used) that has helped students engage with each other online?

Gathertown - a virtual walk through environment
GoReact - video submission and feedback approach to make feedback feel more personal
Github -programming lecturers used it a lot with their classes
Piazza - Posting questions and allowing other students, teachers and Tas to interact/edit answers to solve them.
Breakout rooms
Team quizzes e.g. using Kahoot, TurningPoint
Slack - Text based chat with potential audio/video conferencing.
Virtual meeting spaces – e.g. Mozilla Hubs <https://hubs.mozilla.com/>
Discussion boards
Collaborative and interactive software – useful for groupwork, e.g. Miro

What are the downsides to using technology to facilitate student engagement with each other?

Sometimes the focus becomes the technology not the pedagogy. Major issues with connectivity and poor broadband or bandwidth. Access to technology and digital poverty are real issues. Lack of integration of various learning platforms and apps. Too much variation and new technology can cause confusion and can be overwhelming for students. “Zoom fatigue”.

Are there any activities that we can use, for example in online lectures, to embed social interaction? How do they support good pedagogy?

Display student working and showcase multiple ways of solving a problem. Share power - the lecturer is not necessarily the one with the best method. Portfolio using WordPress, Mozilla Hubs etc. where students can share their work and other students can comment and get used to give constructive feedback and build their confidence to share their own work. Jigsaw activities. Cooperative learning - grouped by experts. Think-pair-share and peer discussion.

How does the environment (fully online, F2F, blended), and group size and dynamic affect the strategies and technologies used?

Found it much easier to get online engagement in first lockdown when we already knew students rather than starting a relationship online. The blend of face-to-face vs online time can make a big difference. Difficult to get large groups who don't know each other to turn on cameras etc. Premade groups don't always work. Positive peer pressure in smaller classes and F2F it is harder to stay hidden.

How do we handle traditional hands-on group projects?

Design build projects adapted by providing kits for students to use at home.

How do we assess if our methods are effective?

Talking with individual students, but it's much more difficult than face-to-face, focus groups, polling students.

When trying to develop structures and environment, the key themes that came out of the discussion were,

1. It is important to try and encourage the use of cameras as much as possible to create a sense of belonging and community.
2. Actively trying to encourage participation in other ways including creating group activities that force students to work together, creating peer feedback activities is one option.
3. Letting activities remain formative remains an issue. Creating activities that carry some summative credit tend to be more successful.

In terms of methods and technology participants felt that,

1. It is too easy to focus on the technology and not the experience, students can be overwhelmed with too many platforms.
2. Poor technology, internet access etc is an ongoing issue for many students, which impacts their ability to fully participate.
3. Creating social activities and social hubs through platforms such as Gather/Mozilla hubs has potential to be useful.

4 SUMMARY

This workshop was an excellent starting point in discussing the complexities of building and maintaining online student communities. The majority of participants felt they gained new ideas on how to encourage students to interact and were keen to try something new in their teaching. Participants found sharing their experiences with colleagues useful. Moving forward an area for investigation is how do we fully understand the student experience and gauge student understanding while using an online environment. Evaluation tools such as forms are useful however they are quite restrictive.

With blended learning at the forefront of engineering education now more than ever, and students engaging predominantly via online both academically and socially, it is vital that we continue to evolve our methods of engagement via online platforms. Not only will this benefit students from a learning perspective it will help facilitate healthy relationships with peers in both a social and professional capacity. This in turn will help students to develop essential skills that will be beneficial in the workplace. Given the likely longer-term impact of changes in professional working environments, which were driven by Covid-19 pandemic, it is important that students gain experiences of effectively interacting remotely and building relationships with colleagues at all levels as this is likely to be a core element of the workplace of the future.

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